

Towards an Intelligent Energy Efficient and Trustworthy 6G M&O Architecture

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Abstract—6G networks aim to further improve QoS while optimizing environmental sustainability metrics, and integrate increased levels of intelligence for automated control and performance optimization. However, directly applying AI/ML-driven decisions can pose risks if the models are not adequately trained. Additionally, balancing performance with energy efficiency is essential due to the high energy demands of complex AI/ML models. Finally, the use of AI/ML introduces additional vulnerabilities that must be mitigated in addition to the need for explainable decisions to ensure trustworthiness. This paper aims to address these aspects by jointly integrating intelligence, energy efficiency, and trustworthiness into M&O for 6G. The proposed framework combines AI/ML-based solutions for dynamic network and service orchestration that optimize performance and energy metrics, and Network Digital Twin management to support AI/ML processes. Additionally, the framework introduces distributed and sustainable MLOps to monitor and further minimize the energy consumption of AI/ML processes, as well as security and explainability mechanisms to enhance the system’s trustworthiness. Evaluations of the framework’s components demonstrate its feasibility and performance.

Index Terms—6G, M&O, Network intelligence, Energy efficiency, trustworthiness

I. INTRODUCTION

Future network technologies are envisioned to natively incorporate higher levels of intelligence, improve data rates, coverage, and latency while minimizing their energy consumption and carbon footprint to meet sustainability goals. Indeed, the IMT 2030 framework identifies a set of capability enhancements and new capabilities to be supported by future 6G networks, these include AI-based capabilities and environmental sustainability [1]. In this context, 6G networks shall integrate intelligent and automated network control that optimizes energy efficiency while satisfying granular performance requirements [2].

However, directly applying AI/ML-based orchestration decisions introduces risks of negatively impacting performance if the model is not adequately trained or updated. To solve this, Network Digital Twins (NDT) have emerged as a tool for safe AI/ML-based control by providing accurate digital replicas of the network. NDTs can be used to observe the

possible effects of orchestration actions on the infrastructure, or generate training data.

In contrast, while integrating intelligence helps improve performance, the training process and inference of complex AI/ML models consumes significant amounts of energy and computing resources [3]. Thus, a trade-off should be sought between performance and energy efficiency when developing and implementing AI/ML-based solutions.

Furthermore, incorporating AI/ML into network control creates new security vulnerabilities [4]. Indeed, adversarial attacks can target the AI/ML models to influence the network orchestration decisions, and privacy attacks can be employed to gain access to sensitive data that are used for e.g. model training. Thus, specific defense strategies are needed to protect AI/ML models against such attacks. Finally, due to the critical impact of the orchestration decisions on the 6G network and services, and to improve the trustworthiness of the AI/ML-based control system, explainability mechanisms are needed to provide human-readable explanations for the AI/ML-driven orchestration decisions.

To address these issues, this paper presents a framework for intelligent, trustworthy, and energy efficient 6G Orchestration and Management (M&O). The contributions of the framework presented in this paper are the following:

- AI/ML-based mechanisms for dynamic M&O that jointly optimize energy and performance metrics.
- The AI/ML-based M&O is supported by NDTs for impact assessment, and MLOps mechanisms to observe and minimize AI/ML model energy consumption.
- Integration of security and explainability aspects into the AI/ML model training process to improve the trustworthiness of the M&O system.
- Framework components are validated with a PoC.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II presents an overview of the related work, section III describes the proposed M&O architecture, section IV provides evaluation results for the framework, section V provides insights and discussions, while section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

Multiple works have studied intelligence and sustainability within 6G. The Zero-touch network and service management (ZSM) reference architecture specified by ETSI [5] allows the full automation of network and service M&O in multi-vendor environments. The framework was extended to support NDTs

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Fig. 1: Proposed architecture for intelligent, energy-efficient and trustworthy 6G M&O

and AI/ML trustworthiness aspects. The paper in [6] explores the integration of AI with 6G to enhance energy efficiency in network management. The authors propose a multi-layer heterogeneous network (HetNet) architecture with a collaborative learning strategy that optimally distributes ML tasks across network layers and entities. This approach aims to address the computational and energy challenges associated with ML tasks in 6G networks. Similarly, [7] proposes a zero-touch management approach that leverages AI methods, specifically Federated Learning (FL) to enhance energy efficiency and scalability in massive network slicing. The developed architecture integrates monitoring, analytics and decision components at the NF, slice, domain and inter-domain levels that can exchange information and coordinate as needed to minimize the overall SLA violations and the energy consumption of both computation and communication resources in the network. However, both works do not assess the amount of energy that is consumed by the AI methods that are used in their orchestration solutions. The authors of [8] propose a novel architecture for Network Slicing that integrates AI/ML-based slice orchestration. The architecture focuses on sustainability and energy efficiency during the slice life-cycle by reducing communication costs, prioritizing resource allocation from providers using renewable energy, and forecasting electricity consumption. Additionally, the framework includes security mechanisms to ensure isolation and integrity for shared infrastructures. However, the proposed security solutions focus on generic security threats, and do not address the specific vulnerabilities that are introduced by AI/ML use for network management. The paper in [9] delves into the integration of AI to enhance security in 6G networks in a sustainable manner by striking a balance between robust security mechanisms and energy efficiency. The proposed solution supports adaptive AI-based security measures to protect network components

against threats targeting AI availability and integrity e.g. data poisoning. To ensure a security-energy trade-off, the framework also includes an intelligent mechanism that customizes security schemes (e.g. encryption algorithm, key length) for users based on device capabilities, energy conditions and their specific vulnerabilities. In [10], a high-level end-to-end 6G blueprint is designed based on a set of requirements and design principles that have been derived from identified 6G use cases, where environmental sustainability, digital inclusiveness and trustworthiness are prioritized. To support the 6G use cases, the blueprint incorporates a set of pervasive functionalities to support data collection, AI/ML, security and privacy, and Orchestration and Management. The authors of [11] devise a solution for ZSM trustworthiness by combining anomaly detection, root cause identification using eXplainable AI (XAI), and Large Language Models to generate and deliver human readable explanations. However, energy efficiency aspects for M&O and AI/ML are not addressed in [9]–[11].

Table I illustrates the contribution of the proposed framework compared to prior art. To the best of our knowledge, the 6G M&O framework in this paper is the first to combine sustainability for both M&O and AI/ML-based control with AI/ML trustworthiness and NDTs. The functional blocks developed within this framework can be integrated into the end-to-end 6G blueprint in [10] by providing the relevant pervasive functionalities.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

This section describes the proposed framework for intelligent, trustworthy and energy efficient M&O for 6G networks and services. The high-level view is illustrated in Figure 1. For the sake of brevity, the infrastructure, Network Function and application layers are omitted in the following descriptions.

	Sustainable M&O with AI/ML	AI/ML Sustainability	Digital Twin	AI/ML Trustworthiness
[5]	✓	X	✓	✓
[6]	✓	✓	X	X
[7]	✓	✓	X	X
[8]	✓	X	X	X
[9]	✓	X	X	✓
[10]	✓	X	✓	✓
[11]	X	X	X	✓
This paper	✓	✓	✓	✓

TABLE I: Feature comparison of the proposed architecture with related works

A. Intelligent and sustainable M&O

This functional block aims to perform intelligent M&O for the 6G system while optimizing performance metrics as well as sustainability goals. It uses AI/ML models and NDTs provided by the AI/ML and NDT management layers to make decisions on M&O operations for supporting service life-cycle management. It also interfaces with the different layer managers to apply the M&O actions. Sustainable M&O operations that are supported by this functional block include function placement and migration, dynamic scaling and resource allocation, task scheduling, and network reconfiguration:

1) *Resource-efficient function placement in the edge*: Edge Computing enables the deployment of distributed services closer to end users, which reduces communication latency and computational load on the network. However, Edge resources are limited, which requires more optimized resource allocation mechanisms. Energy and resource efficiency can then be achieved through consolidation by deploying virtual functions on a limited number of Edge servers to reduce power usage. To this end, an intelligent process can be used to perform dynamic placement of network and service functions and determine the distribution of user demand over the functions with the objective of satisfying performance requirements while minimizing resource usage by consolidating functions on a limited number of edge nodes. This process reduces the number of physical nodes that are used to host services, which ultimately reduces the overall resource and energy consumption.

2) *Energy-efficient resource allocation and task scheduling*: Efficient management of energy resources in future networks is crucial due to the increasing number of wireless devices and their requirements. To this end, a task planning system can optimize the placement of computational tasks across available nodes, such as edge servers, cloud systems, and robotic units, with the aim of maximizing energy efficiency. This is achieved by minimizing the energy consumed for computation, transmission, and leveraging different energy sources such as radio frequency (RF) harvesters or solar panels. The mechanism takes into account task-specific requirements such as data size and location, as well as compute node capabilities including CPU, memory, and power consumption. In robotic use cases, the task planning system can also optimize energy usage by assigning tasks based on robot capabilities, travel distances, and battery levels.

3) *Intelligent network re-configuration*: Similar to previous M&O operations, network re-configuration can be optimized to increase energy savings by dynamically adjusting network

parameters and settings to adapt to changes in network state. This can be particularly useful for radio networks, as radio resource consumption is estimated to make up the majority of the overall energy consumption in network infrastructures. Energy efficiency can then be realized by leveraging AI/ML to select optimal configuration settings for base stations and other network equipment without compromising quality of experience (QoE). Additionally, since some configuration changes may take longer to take effect, accurate predictive models can help anticipate such adjustments.

4) *Distributed and adaptive service scaling*: When optimizing the M&O operations of increasingly complex service graphs, centralized approaches can fall short when addressing the exponential decision space growth. In this context, decentralized multi-agent resource and task management mechanisms can be used to perform distributed and adaptive scaling, where distributed agents operate their own service locally, while also efficiently collaborating to achieve the global objectives such as end-to-end service latency and power consumption. Each agent is responsible for monitoring the service metrics and updating the deployment configuration of the service based on its local model. Additionally, to optimize the global reward across all agents, a collaborative approach can be employed for the training process of the multi-agent system.

5) *Dynamic migration for extreme edge nodes*: Extreme Edge Computing refers to the offloading of computation to end-user or vertical industry devices by virtualizing the end-device resources that are made available to the network, which further reduces service latency. However, this introduces new challenges related to the availability and energy constraints of the extreme edge nodes. Indeed, extreme edge devices may change location or leave the network, or the device may run out of battery. Thus, services should be migrated dynamically between extreme edge nodes based on their availability and energy status while taking into account service-specific constraints. To this end, the status of the extreme edge devices can be periodically assessed to identify the need for migration, and select the migration targets for services based on energy-related information such as the node's battery level or energy type. To further reduce energy consumption, a decentralized approach can be adopted, where a separate AI/ML instance supports orchestration decisions for each service, thereby minimizing computation and energy consumption of the AI/ML model by considering a smaller set of states and actions.

B. Cross-layer monitoring and data collection

This functionality interfaces with the different layers of the architecture and collects data on the state of the network infrastructure and services such as performance and sustainability metrics. The data is provided as input to the AI/ML models in the M&O layer to make control decisions. Monitoring data is also provided to the AI/ML and NDT Management Layers for evaluating model performance and updating the NDTs.

C. AI/ML model Management

This functionality is responsible for orchestrating the life-cycle of AI/ML models that are used by the M&O layer. It

can trigger model training and update, data collection from the monitoring layer, and deployment of the trained models on the inference instances. The model training may be centralized or distributed over multiple instances or domains such as in FL. The model training functionality includes trustworthiness modules for robust adversarial training, secure data exchange to ensure privacy, and explainability exposure. It also includes a sustainability MLOps module to monitor and minimize the energy consumption of the MLOps control loop of the models.

1) *Distributed model training orchestration*: Distributed model training methods such as FL enhance privacy where each distributed agent trains its model locally and only transmits model updates. Given the limited compute capabilities at the network Edge, the distributed model training process should be orchestrated to optimize resource usage and avoid adverse affects on critical network operations. The proposed distributed training orchestrator selects the most relevant data sources. Those should be significantly distinct from each other, as highly correlated data sources minimally contribute to the learning process. Furthermore, the orchestrator considers the proximity of data sources to the Edge infrastructure both in terms of location and capacity of the network links between the data source and the compute resource. For example, the orchestrator would prefer a geographically distant source with a high-capacity fiber-optic link to the edge compute resource over a closer source connected by slow, congested Ethernet links.

Weight sharing and model aggregation are performed asynchronously at various levels of the network compute hierarchy, which minimizes model aggregation at the network core. These sub-aggregated models are then periodically merged at the core to produce the overall model. This approach alleviates the burden of synchronized scheduled aggregation across the entire network, which could negatively impact network operations. Additionally, compute nodes connected to data sources with varying update frequencies may train at different rates. Although this method results in an uneven shared overall model across the network, the dissimilarity becomes less pronounced in the later stages of learning when updates to the aggregated model are less influential.

2) *Intelligent M&O Trustworthiness*: Intelligent M&O trustworthiness refers to the functionalities ensuring that the system is reliable, accurate, secure, explainable, and privacy-preserving while utilizing AI/ML in decision-making. This concept becomes critical when AI/ML and automation are integrated into the operations and management layers of network systems. Intelligent M&O trustworthiness is ensured via: (i) the adversarial training to ensure performance, (ii) data exposure privacy, and (iii) explainability exposure functions that are integrated into model training as shown in Figure 1.

a) *Robust model training*: The performance of the AI/ML algorithms powering M&O systems ought to be ensured since incorrect decisions may cause system failures or create security vulnerabilities. For example, intent-based management (IbM) is becoming crucial for managing and operating 6G systems by interpreting high-level, abstract goals defined through intents. However, IbM systems are vulnerable to adversarial attacks, which can originate from compromised

or malicious components within the system [4]. Tampering with intents can result in misconfigurations or security vulnerabilities, causing the network to perform unauthorized or unintended actions, such as rerouting traffic, granting elevated permissions, or exposing sensitive data. These attacks can affect the performance of the IbM system, leading to incorrect decisions that negatively impact network performance and increase operational costs for network operators. To mitigate those risks, adversarial techniques can be integrated into the training process of the models as shown in Figure 1.

b) *Privacy*: Furthermore, intelligent M&O systems rely on collecting and analyzing large volumes of operational data that may originate from diverse geographical areas, which can introduce privacy concerns. To ensure trustworthiness, these systems must handle sensitive data in a secure manner and ensure full compliance with privacy regulations and security best practices to preserve trust with users, service providers, and regulatory bodies. As previously discussed, FL is a promising solution to avoid transmitting raw data over the network. However, sharing local model updates instead of training data may not be sufficient to address privacy concerns. Therefore, privacy-enhanced FL techniques such as differential privacy or secure multi-party computation can be implemented via the data exposure privacy modules in the framework. These advanced techniques allow the system to aggregate model updates without exposing potentially sensitive features from individual analytics functions, thus ensuring local data privacy.

c) *Explainability*: In addition to security and privacy considerations, AI/ML models operate as black boxes, making their decisions difficult to interpret. This lack of transparency raises concerns about trust, accountability, and the ability to detect and correct errors. To address these challenges, AI/ML decision making must be supported by XAI methods that provide meaningful explanations for AI/ML-based decisions. These explanations can be exposed for human expert review to increase trustworthiness in the M&O system. They can also be used in automated validation procedures to detect anomalies and trigger corrective actions when the model behaves unexpectedly. Indeed, by analyzing the AI/ML model decision process, XAI can help pinpoint the reasons for model performance degradation, where that information can be provided to the model's control loop to fix the performance issues by updating or re-training the model, and optionally collecting new data. The explainability exposure function can jointly implement various XAI techniques to provide explanations at different levels of abstraction. For example, Shapley values can explain individual predictions within a single AI/ML model or quantify the contribution of each AI/ML model within a larger system [12].

3) *MLOps Sustainability*: While MLOps has been widely applied in state-of-the-art solutions to automate the life-cycle management of AI/ML models, there is also a need to reduce the environmental impact of using AI/ML. The Sustainable MLOps (S-MLOps) functionality is designed to integrate sustainability principles into the life-cycle of AI/ML workflows by optimizing energy efficiency while maintaining performance in network operations. It provides a structured approach to automate and optimize AI/ML-based processes

Fig. 2: Operational scope of the proposed Sustainable MLOps (S-MLOps) functionality

within 6G and cloud-native environments using energy consumption measurements in the different stages of MLOps workflows.

S-MLOps implements energy-aware MLOps by incorporating real-time power monitoring tools which track CPU, GPU, and memory usage to evaluate energy consumption, collect data related to greenhouse gas equivalent generation, then provide model sustainability metrics. The framework enables dynamic resource allocation, ensuring that AI model training and inference are executed on the most energy-efficient hardware and time without compromising computational accuracy. In addition, it includes APIs that expose energy consumption metrics, allowing operators to make informed decisions.

As shown in Figure 2, the implementation of S-MLOps supports modular deployments by facilitating multi-stakeholder collaboration between network operators, software vendors, and AI model developers [13]. It provides automation tools that support workflow orchestration, model sharing, and sustainable AI/ML life-cycle management. A key feature is its model evaluation capability mechanism that ranks models based on both performance and sustainability metrics, which supports MLOps decisions that minimize the carbon footprint. Indeed, based on their complexity, AI/ML models consume varying amounts of energy for their training or operation. Thus, this information is beneficial when creating and maintaining MLOps workflows to identify the stages that are consuming more energy, and take energy saving actions while keeping a trade-off with performance metrics.

D. Network Digital Twin Management

This functional block is responsible for NDT generation and update by interfacing with the monitoring layer to collect the required data for the NDT. The NDT instance may be used by the M&O to safely assess the effect of orchestration actions before applying them on the network. As previously discussed, directly applying AI-based M&O decisions on the live network might negatively impact the network and services. On the other hand, given the envisaged complexity of the 6G network, maintaining a live replica for configuration testing prior to production deployments becomes unfeasible. For these reasons, NDTs are an apt solution for providing a logical replica of the live network as a staging area. The credibility of the NDT depends on how accurately it: (i) captures the

varying state of the network and (ii) predicts the effect that proposed changes will have on running services.

Therefore, it is necessary to generate an accurate NDT of the network infrastructure which reflects its behavior and properties such as virtualization, captures the intricacies of diverse topologies, and scales well to various network sizes.

In real-time operation, when the M&O is triggered to perform a life-cycle management operation such as a new service deployment, it determines the network configurations to perform the operation and applies them on the NDT. The NDT then predicts the resulting performance for that service if deployed and the effect on already running services. The results of this prediction are fed back to the M&O which determines whether the new service should be admitted. If the predicted performance is such that the new service would adversely affect already running services and/or its KPIs cannot be met, the orchestrator rejects the request. Otherwise, the orchestrator applies the configurations on the production network to provision the service. To maintain NDT accuracy, the monitoring function periodically pulls data from the production network and provides it to the NDT training and update module to improve future predictions.

IV. EVALUATION

To validate the proposed framework, this section provides the evaluation of PoC implementations of the following components: dynamic migration algorithm from the sustainable M&O functionality, S-MLOps, and robust model training.

A. Dynamic migration in extreme edge

To perform dynamic migration of services across extreme edge nodes as described in section III-A5, a small model was trained using DQN with one hidden layer of 64 neurons to select the target node for migration where energy-related metrics are considered. The training environment was deployed using a simulator [14] based on K3S which comprises 15 worker nodes representing the extreme edge nodes, and a service instance that is deployed on one of the nodes. The model input for each step consists of periodical status information from the extreme edge devices which includes the node availability, battery level and energy type (sustainable or fossil).

The output provided by the model consists of the ID of the node where the service should be placed next, and the

Fig. 3: Scores of the extreme edge dynamic migration model

migration is triggered by setting the node affinity of the deployment in K3S. The model reward was computed based on the battery level of the source and target nodes with the goal of minimizing the overall number of migrations to reduce impact on services. Additional rewards are provided if the service is placed on a node with a sustainable energy type or if it is migrated to a nearby node to minimize impact on service latency. The rewards per episode are illustrated in Figure 3. Once the model is trained, the obtained decision policy is tested over 500 episodes where each episode comprises 10 timesteps. Based on those results, the average number of migrations per episode was 2.5 migrations, the average battery level at which the migration is triggered was 59%, and the average battery level of target nodes was 68%. These results show that the model’s decision policy minimizes the number of migrations, and keeps the services on extreme edge nodes when possible, then migrates the service to nodes with higher battery levels. It was also seen that nodes with sustainable energy sources were selected 71% of the times, while only half of the nodes had sustainable energy. These performance results are similar to those obtained by the DQN model in [15], which has an average of 1.8–2.4 migrations per 10 time-steps for a scenario involving 9 edge nodes. However, the model in [15] uses a NN of 3 layers of 128 neurons per layer, while our proposed model only has one layer of 64 neurons. This highlights the performance and energy efficiency tradeoff that can be achieved by our proposed solution as more complex models of larger sizes consume more computational power and energy.

B. AI/ML adversarial training for Trustworthiness

To validate the robust model training component described in section III-C2, a trained model is evaluated against adversarial attacks, specifically FGSM and BIM, by comparing its performance before and after adversarial training as described in [4]. Table II presents a comparison of Mean Squared Error (MSE) values before and after incorporating adversarial examples. It can be seen that the original model achieves low MSE on clean data, which confirms effective model training. The adversarially trained (robust) model also maintains a low

MSE on clean data, which suggests that the defense strategy does not compromise natural performance. Under FGSM and BIM attacks, the original model experiences a rise in MSE, whereas the robust model demonstrates better resistance, with a smaller increase in error.

TABLE II: MSE values of the original and robust models before and after applying adversarial attacks

	MSE without attack	MSE black-box	MSE white-box
FGSM attack			
Original Model	0.01379	0.03183	0.03786
Robust Model	0.01430	0.02130	0.02401
BIM attack			
Original Model	0.01379	0.03239	0.03856
Robust Model	0.01430	0.02158	0.02451

C. S-MLOps

MLOps workflows		Energy (kWh)	Carbon (egrCO ₂)	Share (%)	Scope
Data Acq.	Dataset Build	0.0075	1	21	Provider
	Context	0.0005	0.06		
Training	Process	0.0023	0.3	54	Provider
	Push	0.0015	0.2		
	Trainer	0.016	2.1		
Evaluation	Context	0.0006	0.075	14	Provider/ CSP
	Trainer	0.0052	0.68		
	Context	0.0001	0.02		
Execution	Inference	0.0021	0.27	8	Provider/ CSP
	Context	0.0009	0.12		
Model Acq.	Acq.	0.001	0.134	3	CSP
	Context	0.0002	0.02		

TABLE III: Energy Consumption and Carbon Emissions for different phases of the S-MLOps Workflows

To validate the capabilities of the S-MLOps component described in section III-C3, a test environment was set up to simulate a telecommunications scenario involving a software vendor and a mobile network operator. Each domain was deployed as a Kubernetes cluster, with independent but interconnected MLOps workflows configured through the S-MLOps functionality [13]. The vendor-side workflow was designed for the training and validation of AI/ML-based network services, incorporating data storage, workflow orchestration, and energy consumption monitoring, along with a mechanism for sharing trained models. On the mobile network side, the workflow focused on dataset creation and model deployment, including processes for production data simulation and inference. For the evaluation, a model for extreme-edge device status prediction was used in the MLOps workflow [13], where the model includes 4 layers of 32-96 neurons. The training and evaluation dataset was obtained from a dedicated extreme-edge simulation environment [14].

A detailed analysis of energy consumption and carbon emissions was performed for each MLOps workflow stage. The results confirm the feasibility of the proposed S-MLOps approach, and its ability to orchestrate MLOps workflows while integrating sustainability monitoring. The results, summarized in Table III, present the energy consumption and carbon emissions associated with each stage, which provide a quantitative assessment of the environmental impact of MLOps

workflows. It can be seen that the training phase consumes the most energy and produces the most carbon emissions, making up for 54% of the total values for the whole MLOps workflow, while the execution phase only constitutes 8% of the total values. This underlines the importance of optimizing the (re-)training process, in particular to minimize the energy consumption and carbon emissions of the MLOps workflow. Furthermore, the results highlight the potential of leveraging energy consumption metrics in multiple ways. These metrics can be incorporated as contextual model information, which enables model selection based not only on conventional performance indicators (e.g., accuracy) but also on energy efficiency and carbon footprint. Hence, S-MLOps serves as a powerful tool for achieving energy efficient 6G network automation by ensuring that AI-driven systems operate with optimized power efficiency and reduced environmental impact.

V. DISCUSSION

While this framework primarily targets future 6G networks, it can also be integrated with current 5G deployments, more specifically the Management Services (MnS) and Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF) as specified by 3GPP by providing AI/ML models supporting the management decision logic. In this vein, the framework is also compatible with O-RAN architectures, as it can provide the AI/ML models for performing Non-Real Time and Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Control (RIC), as well as ETSI ZSM. The proposed framework can be easily deployed by network operators and industry practitioners by connecting it to the relevant interfaces for data collection and M&O operation implementation, where the framework trains and maintains AI/ML models for automated M&O on the underlying infrastructure. Thanks to its modularity, the architecture can also be extended to support additional components and M&O operations.

However, while Section IV provides a feasibility assessment of the framework by implementing and evaluating 3 selected components, the evaluation remains limited in scale. Further insights could be obtained with a system-wide performance evaluation of the framework in real-world networks considering the full life-cycle of a service and implementing all of the framework components.

In addition, although the framework includes mechanisms to minimize energy and resource consumption, the integration of AI/ML in M&O, MLOps workflows and the use of NDTs for M&O action verification introduces additional overhead and latency in the network control process. This aspect should be further explored in future works.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an intelligent M&O framework for 6G which also optimizes energy efficiency and trustworthiness. The framework includes functional blocks that enable AI/ML model management with MLOps sustainability and distributed learning orchestration mechanisms, where AI/ML training can also be supported by Network Digital Twins. The training process also includes security, privacy and explainability mechanisms to ensure trustworthiness. The proposed framework was validated through PoC evaluations of different components.

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REFERENCES

- [1] International Telecommunication Union, "Imt-2030 framework," ITU Radiocommunication Sector, Tech. Rep. M.2160, 2023, accessed: March 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/m/R-REC-M.2160-0-202311-1!!PDF-E.pdf
- [2] S. Prasad Tera, R. Chinthaginjala, G. Pau, and T. Hoon Kim, "Toward 6g: An overview of the next generation of intelligent network connectivity," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 925–961, 2025.
- [3] R. Schwartz, J. Dodge, N. A. Smith, and O. Etzioni, "Green ai," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 63, no. 12, p. 54–63, Nov. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3381831>
- [4] L. Karaçay, A. C. Baktir, R. Fuladi *et al.*, "Secure ai/ml-based control in intent-based management system," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)*, 2024, pp. 618–623.
- [5] ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) ZSM, "Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Reference Architecture," European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), ETSI Group Specification GS ZSM 002 V1.1.1, August 2019, Accessed: 2025-07-23.
- [6] M. A. Hossain, A. R. Hossain, and N. Ansari, "Ai in 6g: Energy-efficient distributed machine learning for multilayer heterogeneous networks," *IEEE Network*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 84–91, 2022.
- [7] H. Chergui, L. Blanco, L. A. Garrido *et al.*, "Zero-touch ai-driven distributed management for energy-efficient 6g massive network slicing," *IEEE Network*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 43–49, 2021.
- [8] J. S. B. Martins, T. C. Carvalho, R. Moreira *et al.*, "Enhancing network slicing architectures with machine learning, security, sustainability and experimental networks integration," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 69 144–69 163, 2023.
- [9] S. Shen, C. Yu, K. Zhang, J. Ni, and S. Ci, "Adaptive and dynamic security in ai-empowered 6g: From an energy efficiency perspective," *IEEE Commun. Standards Magazine*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 80–88, 2021.
- [10] S. Kerboeuf, P. Porambage, A. Jain *et al.*, "Design methodology for 6g end-to-end system: Hexa-x-ii perspective," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 3368–3394, 2024.
- [11] A. Mekrache, M. Mekki, A. Ksentini, B. Brik, and C. Verikoukis, "On combining xai and llms for trustworthy zero-touch network and service management in 6g," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 154–160, 2025.
- [12] F. Ruggeri, W. Emanuelsson, A. Terra, R. Inam, and K. H. Johansson, "Rollout-based Shapley Values for Explainable Cooperative Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning," in *2024 IEEE Int. Conf. on Mach. Learn. for Communication and Networking (ICMLCN)*. IEEE, pp. 227–233.
- [13] Atos R&I, "Hx-mlops: A scalable and sustainable mlops framework," GitHub repository, 2024, accessed: March 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Atos-Research-and-Innovation/HX-MLOps>
- [14] —, "Infrastructure layer emulator (ile)," GitHub repository, 2024, accessed: March 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Atos-Research-and-Innovation/INFRASTRUCTURE-LAYER-EMULATOR>
- [15] A. Sarah, G. Nencioni, and M. M. Islam Khan, "Drl-based availability-aware migration of a mec service," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 5088–5102, 2024.

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